

Determination and Characterization of Oil Palm Petiole Fibre Content

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Abstract: Oil palm Petiole fibre (OPPF) is undoubtedly the most significant solid waste by-product within the palm oil sector. This solid waste component contains cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, which make up the bulk of the biomass. The high content of these organic materials in OPPF makes them a valuable resource for various applications. The utilization of OPPF not only helps in reducing waste but also contributes to sustainable practices in the palm oil industry. Additionally, nanocellulose, a lightweight solid material derived from plant matter and composed of nanosized cellulose fibrils—can be extracted from this waste. A study was carried out to determine the organic content of oil palm petiole fibre using the Klason method and to evaluate the capability of oil palm petiole fibre (OPPF) for nanocellulose production. Empty oil palm petiole was initially subjected to an alkali treatment, followed by a bleaching process, and then nanocellulose was produced through acid hydrolysis using H₂SO₄. The end products were analyzed through X-ray diffraction. The X-Ray Diffraction shows the crystallinity index of OPPF-CNC as 54.5%, 62.3% and 65% respectively. The cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin content were also discovered to be 44.75%; 24.37% and 30.85% respectively. The positive outcomes confirm that OPPF is an excellent source for nanocellulose, with the organic biomass being suitable for processing into other products.

Keywords: Cellulose; Hemicellulose; Lignin; Oil Palm Petiole fibre, Nanocellulose

Introduction

The African oil palm, native to the Gulf of Guinea in West Africa, is scientifically called *Elaeis guineensis* Jacq (Almeida-Naranjo *et al.*, 2022; Aguilar *et al.*, 2022).

The oil palm tree is heavily farmed in Nigeria and is recognized as a significant cash crop, offering numerous benefits such as food, shelter, household products, and employment opportunities (Mehanny *et al.*, 2021; Nwosu *et al.*, 2022). Despite the

numerous benefits and opportunities provided by the oil palm tree, it yields a notable quantity of solid waste at the completion of its life cycle. This byproduct primarily comprises large quantities of lignocellulosic material from the oil palm- (Habbak and Emad, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2020; Persade and Ikna, 2020).

The chemical composition of the Oil palm Petiole fibre (OPPF) consists mainly of lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose. OPPF chemical structure is dominated by lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose, with cellulose accounting for 37.50% (Awang *et al.*, 2023; Noah *et al.*, 2022, Persade and Ikna, 2020). The qualities of OPPF can change according to factors like the plant's age, size and stage of development, geographical location, soil conditions, climate where the oil palm is cultivated and the testing methods employed (Mishra *et al.*, 2022, Persade and Ikna, 2020). Cellulose is the primary component, making up about 37%, and is closely linked to hemicellulose and lignin. Isolating cellulose involves extensive chemical processing. Cellulose is made up of D-glucose units bonded by β -1,4-glycosidic linkages. Lignin, on the other hand, is a three-dimensional phenylpropanoid polymer, characterized by various carbon-to-carbon bonds and additional bonds between phenylpropane units, which are difficult to hydrolyze (Persade and Ikna, 2020). Hemicellulose is typically found chemically linked to polysaccharides, proteins, or lignin. It dissolves more readily than cellulose and is extractable from wood. Hemicellulose differs from cellulose as it has more robust bonds and is somewhat easier to break down into monomers. Its high content plays a significant role in bonding fibre together, as hemicellulose functions as an adhesive

between individual fibre (Intan *et al.*, 2020, Valle *et al.*, 2022).

The cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose compounds present in OPPF can be converted into valuable products such as biofuel (Kolajo *et al.*, 2024), lactic acid (Li *et al.*, 2020), bio-composites and bioplastics. Additionally, cellulose can be used to manufacture different green products, including sugar, polylactic acid (PLA) for bioplastics, vanillin, and food additives, lignin-based adhesives and activated carbon. Klason's lignin analysis directly assesses lignin content in biomass by hydrolyzing carbohydrates with concentrated acid, resulting in lignin residue that is quantified through gravimetric analysis (Intan, 2020).

Materials and Methods

Materials used

Oil palm petiole used in this study was collected from an oil palm plantation in Umuagwo-Ohaji, Imo State, Nigeria, and this served as the raw material. The reagents used included sodium hypochlorite (NaClO, 4%), glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH, 99.7%), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, beads, Merck), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), and distilled water. All chemicals were reagent grade and were used as supplied. Reagent-grade chemicals were used in their provided state.

Preparation of oil palm petiole

Three oil palm petiole was cut from three different palm trees in Umuagwo, Imo State. The oil palm petiole fibre (OPPF) was cut into small pieces (approximately 2-3 cm) and thoroughly washed to remove dust, dirt, wax, and other contaminants. After the washing process, the samples were fully dried in open air and then ground to a size of about 2 mm using a manual grinding

apparatus. The crushed material was stored in an airtight container.

Isolation of nanocellulose

The dried powdered oil palm petiole samples (50 g) was treated with 500 ml of a 2% (w/v) sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution for 3 hours at 70°C while being stirred magnetically. After filtering the mixture, the filtrate was cleaned extensively with distilled water to completely remove any residual alkali from the surface.

The filtrate (fibrous material) was placed into a beaker that held 450 ml of distilled water and a 4% (w/v) sodium hypochlorite solution, with a few drops of glacial acetic acid added to adjust the pH to 4. The mixture was boiled for 8 hours at 70–80°C to bleach the fibrous material. After bleaching, the fibrous material was filtered, and the filtrate was extensively rinsed with distilled water until the material's pH was adjusted to 7. The material was subsequently air-dried and kept in a sealed container.

The purpose of these alkali pretreatments was to remove the hemicelluloses and lignin content. The alkali-treated fibrous material was then hydrolyzed in a 60 wt% sulfuric acid solution, boiled at 46°C for 30 minutes with careful agitation. To cease the reaction, tenfold the volume of distilled water was used. The diluted suspension was spun at 3000 rpm for 30 minutes to separate the precipitate. The collected precipitate was then dialyzed for 3 days with a cellulose membrane until a consistent pH was reached.

Determination of lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose content of the oil palm petiole fiber

Determination of lignin

The lignin amount of the oil palm petiole fibre was determined by the Klasons method (Galiwango *et al.*, 2018). Two hundred milligram (200mg) of the sample was weighed into a beaker. Additionally, 1 ml of 72% sulfuric acid (as determined by specific gravity) was added for every 100 mg of the sample. The mixture was then placed in a water bath at 300°C and stirred regularly to ensure thorough dissolution. After exactly 1 hour, it was diluted with 28 ml of water for each 1 ml of acid and transferred to a 125-ml flask. The secondary hydrolysis was conducted in an autoclave at 120°C for 1 hour. The hot solution was then filtered through fritted glass, and the Klason lignin residue was washed with hot water to remove any remaining acid. The crucibles with the samples are dried to a constant weight at 105°C and then weighed to the nearest 0.1 mg. Lignin content is reported as a percentage of the original sample.

$$\text{Lignin, \%} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Determination of cellulose

Two grams (2g) of the extractive free sample was measured using a weighing balance and put into a 250ml beaker and 100ml of 17.5% NaOH solution was added

and stirred at 25°C for 30 minutes. The content of the beaker was then filtered, washed with 25 ml of 9.5% NaOH solution and 20 ml portion of 100 ml distilled water. The residue was rinsed again with distilled water and 40 ml of 10% acetic acid and further with 1 L distilled water. The residue was then dried at 105°C for 24 hours to constant weight.

$$\text{Cellulose, \%} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Determination of hemicellulose

$$\text{Hemi-Cellulose, \%} = 100 - (\% \text{Cellulose} + \% \text{lignite})$$

Characterization Analysis

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

The phase characteristics of both raw OPPF and isolated cellulose was analyzed using an X-ray diffractometer (D8-Advance Bruker-AXS). The analysis was conducted with a wavelength of 1.540 Å (CuKα radiation), a

scan speed of 2° per second, and a 2θ range of 2–80°. The crystallinity index (CI_x) was subsequently determined using the following formula (Susi *et al.*, 2023).

CI_x was calculated using the formula:

$$CI_x = [(I_{002} - I_{am}) / I_{002}] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where I₀₀₂ represents the maximum peak intensity of the crystalline regions, and I_{am} corresponds to the minimum peak intensity of the amorphous regions.

The crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer's formula." (Susi *et al.*, 2023),

$$D = K / \beta \cos(\theta) \quad (2)$$

where, *K* is the constant 0.91, *θ* is Bragg's angle, and *β* is the intensity of the full width at half of the maximum (FWHM) corresponding to a high intensity peak of the diffraction plane 002.

Results and Discussion

Percentage composition of fibre content

Table 1 Percentage composition of prepared raw fibre samples

Fibre content	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Percentage (%)
Lignin(%)	30.88	29.36	32.4	30.88
Cellulose(%)	44.75	45.90	43.60	44.75

Hemicellulose(%)	24.37	24.74	24.00	24.37
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The proximate analysis of the OPPF waste sample's raw materials is detailed in Table 1. Cellulose, has a molecular formula of $(C_6H_5O_{10})_n$ and consists of a linear polymer of glucose molecules connected by β (1, 4) glycosidic linkages. The cellulose content is reported as 44.75%.

Cellulose interacts with both hemicellulose and lignin. In this study, the lignin and hemicellulose contents were determined to be 30.88% and 24.37%, respectively. Lignin surrounds microfibril cellulose in a

hydrophobic matrix and is chemically attached to both cellulose and hemicellulose. These results align with the conclusions of other research where cellulose in OPPF ranges from 23.7% to 65.0%, hemicellulose from 20.58% to 33.52%, and lignin from 14.1% to 30.45 % (Chang, 2014).

X-Ray diffraction analysis

XRD patterns were collected to determine the crystallinity index of the OPPF, bleached OPPF and nanocellulose derived from the OPPF (Fig.1-3)

Figure 1 XRD Raw fibre

Figure 2 XRD Bleached fibre

Figure 3 XRD Acid hydrolysed fibre

The degree of crystallinity quantifies the proportion between ordered (crystalline) and disordered (amorphous) phases in cellulose. This measure of cellulose crystallinity is accustomed to assess thermal stability, pliability, absorptive capacity, and other physical properties relevant to industrial applications. A higher crystallinity typically enhances rigidity and stiffness, which can improve the mechanical properties of nanocomposites produced from these nanostructures. (Chieng *et al.*, 2017; Akinjokun *et al.*, 2021).

Figures 1 to 3 display the X-ray diffractograms for (a) Raw OPPF, (b) Bleached OPPF, and (c) CNC (Nanocellulose).

Raw OPPF consist of both unordered (amorphous) and highly ordered (crystalline) components (Fig. 1). Therefore, the low peak intensity observed in the cellulose fibers may be due to their entrapment within the amorphous hemicellulose and lignin.

All samples exhibit a distinct peak at a 2θ value of 22° , suggesting the crystalline

nature of cellulose. This is the only peak ($2\theta = 22.06^\circ$) observed in the reflective pattern of the raw OPPF. This may result from amorphous cementing materials coating the crystalline regions of the fibre. Furthermore, a broad peak around 18° is detected, corresponding to the amorphous structure, confirming that OPPF displays the characteristic cellulose I pattern. (Chieng *et al.*, 2017; Anuj *et al.*, 2014; Akinjokun *et al.*, 2021). Two additional crystalline peaks at 2θ values of 15.82° and 34.63° appeared in the diffractogram after the raw OPPF underwent alkaline treatment and bleaching to become bleached OPPF. Bleached OPPF exhibits three peaks at 15.82° , 22.48° , and 34.63° , corresponding to the (110), (002), and (023) crystallographic planes of cellulose I polymorph, indicating that the bleached OPPF has a typical cellulose I structure. (Rosli *et al.*, 2013). Figure 3.2 reveals that the $2\theta = 22.48^\circ$ peak in the bleached OPPF diffractogram is sharper and of higher intensity than that of the raw OPPF. This could be due to the dissolution

of amorphous hemicelluloses and lignin, leading to the recovery of the fibre's crystalline structure, and producing the more pronounced and narrower peaks observed in bleached OPPF.

Cellulose Nano crystals (CNC) isolated via acid hydrolysis also exhibits three peaks at $2\theta = 15.97^\circ$, 22.63° , and 34.63° . However, slight shifts in peak positions are observed, along with increased intensity and peak narrowing. The amorphous background is marked by low diffraction intensity around $2\theta = 18^\circ$. (Akinjokun *et al.*, 2021, Prasannakumar *et al.*, 2022). Table 2 reveals that the crystallinity index (CrI) of raw OPPF, bleached OPPF, and cellulose nanocrystals isolated from OPPF were 54.5%, 62.3%, and 65%, respectively. This highlights the increasing crystallinity of the materials following each stage of chemical treatment. The higher crystallinity index results from the extraction of amorphous constituents and the rearrangement of

crystalline regions into a more structured configuration. (Rosli *et al.*, 2013; Chieng *et al.*, 2017; Susi *et al.*, 2023). The progressive increase in CrI found in this study is consistent with the trend seen during CNC isolation from mulberry bark (Li *et al.*, 2009; Prasannakumar *et al.*, 2022) and *agave angustifolia* (Rosli *et al.*, 2013), and oil palm trunk (Lamaming *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, the simultaneous growth and realignment of monocrystals can lead to increased cellulose crystallinity and sharper diffraction peaks, as demonstrated by the XRD analysis.

The crystalline index (CrI) was subsequently determined using an empirical method based on the equation (1) provided by (NurHayati *et al.*, 2017).

$$CI_x = [(I_{002} - I_{am}) / I_{002}] \times 100 \quad (1),$$

Where I_{002} represents the peak intensity of the crystalline phase and I_{am} denotes the minimum intensity of the amorphous phase in the sample.

Table 2 Crystalline index (%) of Raw OPPF, Bleached OPPF and CNC

Sample	Crystallinity index (Cr1)%
Raw OPPF	54.5
Bleached OPPF	62.3
CNC(Nanocellulose)	65

Conclusion

The substantial cellulose content in oil palm petiole fibre suggests its potential as a raw material for producing hydrogels and other materials. The cellulose derived from OPPF demonstrates significant potential in both attributes and amount, suggesting that the oil palm industry should utilize it comprehensively to develop high-value industrial products. These encouraging findings validate that OPPF is an excellent source for nanocellulose production, and the organic material can be utilized as a feedstock for other products.

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